

Energy Storage needs for clean Power Systems and the potential support from Electrical Vehicles

A simplified assessment on Romanian case

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Abstract— It is a fact that the latest time period shown a technology shift trend in both power systems and electrical vehicles, by the increasing use of electrical storage technology. The recent success in both domains shows clearly that energy storage is a significant game changer and that new horizons need to be scrutinized. The paper makes a preliminary assessment on the long-term impact of storage for power systems and for electrical vehicles, in conditions of targeting a 100% CO₂ free energy production, by making an estimation of storage capacity needed for both domains: power system and electrical vehicles, applied as a simplified assessment on the Romanian case. For estimating the storage needs, the paper presents simulations of renewable energy production based on existing patterns in the Romanian Power System, upscaled to fit a 100% CO₂ free energy production on selected weekly intervals compared with week-based consumption profiles. The paper shows that strong or full penetration of electrical vehicles has the potential to be main driver in helping power systems to mitigate stochastic renewable production with the necessary storage means, to pursue 100% clean energy goals. Moreover, the two domains have synergies and reciprocally help each-other in reaching a global goal of clean energy and transportation.

Keywords— energy storage, power systems, renewables, 100% CO₂ free, electrical vehicles

I. CONDITIONS FOR THE CHANGE AND CURRENT STUDIES

The year 2017 can be coined as being the corner-stone of energy storage boom. There were many signs for considering this statement, for both power system domain and for electrical vehicles.

For power systems several important events occurred:

- The Aliso Canyon disaster in 2015, when dangerous leakages from a gas reservoir have been reported, asking for the facility to be closed, thus endangering production of some gas-based peak-power plants in California; this difficult situation has been mitigated by starting a program for acquiring till 2021 a capacity of 1.3 GW of power produced only by storage means [1], which determined fast-track acquisitions in 2016, such that in early 2017 a capacity of 105 MW and 420 MWh of Li-Ion batteries have been commissioned in record time. The Californian pattern was the requirement that

the energy capacity $E_{\text{BAT}_{\text{nom}}}$ is able to supply a period of 4 hours with the nominal power of the battery $P_{\text{BAT}_{\text{nom}}}$, thus giving a ratio $K = E_{\text{BAT}_{\text{nom}}} / P_{\text{BAT}_{\text{nom}}} = 4$; the ratio shows the main scope of the battery which is to serve evening peak periods of up to four hours and to compensate gas-fired peakers shortages;

- The coal-based shift-out plants in Australia brought blackouts, in conditions of weak grid and of increased renewables [2]. Grid-size batteries started to be seen as one of the potential solutions to bring in short time more flexibility in the grid and different projects have been considered, one being the project for 100 MW and 117 MWh battery enforcement, which has been commissioned at the end of 2017. The factor $K = 1.17$ shows that the battery is intended to mitigate wind production peaks as well as some additional short term services for the grid;
- High penetration of renewables, with stochastic production and reducing the system inertia brought the need for higher dynamics of primary frequency regulation, above the traditional primary f control (or its newer name frequency containment reserve), which asked for 30 seconds time of complete engagement, after up to 2 seconds of delay; the new 10 or 2 seconds reaction time primary fast frequency regulations have been already acquired through bids in UK (200 MW) [3], while different smaller projects for grid stabilisation appeared in Germany (e.g. [4]), and all have been supported by battery based solutions. In fact, using batteries for different grid services is already studied in recent papers [5][6][7][8][9], which show the flexibility and advantages of this technology compared with the traditional solutions;

For electrical vehicles (EVs) important events also occurred:

- The Gigafactory 1 construction, with a capacity of 35 GWh of Li-Ion batteries planned for 2018 [10], most of them to be used in the electrical vehicle domain;
- The 2017 and early 2018 cascading announcements from most of the car manufacturers that they already produce or come soon on the market with a variety of electrical vehicles;

- National policies of important countries such as China and India, to support electrical vehicles;
- Political endorsement of clean transportation coming from countries to ban ICE cars in 2040 [11][12] or to restrict access of classic cars in the center of highly polluted cities [13].
- Increasing interest and advancements in the autopilot solutions, which are possible only with electrical vehicles solutions.

A recent report shows that in 2017 has been deployed a total of 1.4 GW and 2.3 GWh of energy storage, with Australia having the highest total power capacity of 246 MW, while the U.S. reaching the highest energy capacity of 431 MWh [14].

All these actions are strongly pushed by the climate change and increased pollution concerns, but also by the request of increased resilience, as a mitigation to natural disasters.

In this context, several studies were focused to analyse the feasibility of 100% CO₂ free or 100% RES (renewable energy sources) electricity production in general terms [15], the operational concerns due to fluctuations in renewables sources as potentially limiting the ultimate potential for high penetrations of renewables [16], of the EV scenarios evolution [17] of the impact of high EV penetration [18]. Energy storage needs to mitigate high penetration of renewables has been studied in both isolated grids [19], including islands [20], or at a national power system level [21]. The impact of vehicle to grid (V2G) on grids has been also addressed in different studies [22][23].

Even if the V2G technology is more and more considered as a helpful technology for supporting the grid, there is little activity for studying how big is the potential of EVs to help overall the grid in its aim towards full decarbonisation and there is no awareness about which of these economy segments will drive the other.

II. ROMANIAN POWER SYSTEM SCENARIOS FOR 100% CO₂ FREE PRODUCTION – UPSCALING AND STORAGE NEED ESTIMATION

The Romanian power system uses various types of production technologies: fossil fuel-based (coal and gas), hydro, nuclear (2 groups of 700 MW) and more recently, due to attractive incentives, wind, solar and biomass-based renewables. Figure 1 shows a typical mix of energies obtained over a whole day with all technologies.

Figure 1 – Energy mix in 24 hours: example on a typical summer day for the Romanian power system

To be noted that storage energy is also considered in the figure, but it is zero for the base case.

To simulate a situation with 100% CO₂ free production, coal and gas production can be phased out by simulation and wind + solar production can be increased such that we can cover the whole consumption by using these renewables plus nuclear and hydro generation, the latest being considered as classic renewable, which is mainly dispatchable, compared with the new ones which are stochastic in nature.

Figure 2 presents such upscaling of PV and wind production in order to meet in the simulation, together with nuclear and hydro production, the whole weekly consumption energy. It has been chosen a winter period when solar production is normally low and wind production is significant. The simulation is based on hourly average production on each type of technology and on hourly average consumption. The data is obtained from ENTSO-E transparency portal [24]. The rescaled curves are according with the equations (1) below:

$$P_{sim}(\Delta T_i)_{COAL} = P_{rec}(\Delta T_i)_{COAL} * K_{COAL} \quad (1.1)$$

$$P_{sim}(\Delta T_i)_{PV} = P_{rec}(\Delta T_i)_{PV} * K_{PV} \quad (1.5)$$

$$P_{sim}(\Delta T_i)_{WIND} = P_{rec}(\Delta T_i)_{WIND} * K_{WIND} \quad (1.6)$$

$$P_{sim}(\Delta T_i)_{BIO} = P_{rec}(\Delta T_i)_{BIO} * K_{BIO} \quad (1.7)$$

where on the left side are the average hourly P_{sim} powers after rescaling, on the right side are real recorded average powers P_{rec} , the K factors are scaling factors for each technology and ΔT_i represents each time interval of one hour in the studied timeframe of one week.

Figure 2 – Production and consumption over a whole winter week, in the January period 01-07.01.2017

Scaling recorded profiles of both generation and consumption give a good approximation for a future scenario with high RES penetration, by considering similar weather conditions for both wind and solar, while choosing similar conditions for the load evolution. To be noted that consumption has been not scaled, considering that potential future increase of consumption is compensated by a similar increase in energy efficiency. However, scenarios with increased consumption may be analysed as well with the same simulated load-shape rescaling approach.

The needed upscale factors for renewables and the phaseout of fossil-based production are presented in Table 1. The today situation has a scaling factor 1 for all technologies, but the simulation which covers entire consumption with CO₂ free technologies needs different scaling factors, e.g. zero for coal and gas production. The factors for PV and wind production have been increased by choosing different values, until the energy production was slightly higher than the consumption.

Table 1 – Upscale of renewables and production phaseout for technologies with CO₂ emissions

Scaling factors for each production technology	Today	Simulation (rescaling)
Coal: K_{COAL}	1	0
Gas: K_{GAS}	1	0
Hydro: K_{HYDRO}	1	1
Nuclear: K_{NUCL}	1	1
PV: K_{PV}	1	15.5
Wind: K_{WIND}	1	3
Biomass: K_{BIO}	1	2

To be noted that it has been given priority to higher PV production, as this is more easily to be scaled, is expected to become more competitive in the future and can be deployed nearly everywhere in the country, as the solarisation in Romania has only a small depreciation in the North, comparing to south (around 12-15% is the maximum difference all over the country, except some minor regions in the mountains region). It is also expected that large distributed PV deployments will ask for less grid reinforcement at high voltage level, thus a more credible pathway can be implemented when expecting opposition of citizen to many new HV lines. The following weekly energies have been calculated within the presented scenario:

Table 2 – Energy consumption and production during the winter week from Figure 2, based on the Table 1 upscaling factors

Description	Energy /week [GWh]	[%] from cons.
Total production	1255	103
Consumption	1216	100
Hydro	249	20.51
Nuclear	233	18.39
PV	168	13.85
Wind	599	49.29

The calculations shown that the high scaling of PV production (15.5 times more than today installation of around 1.3 GW) achieved a good share of 13.85% even in winter period, being complemented by nearly 50% share of wind production, which is expected during winter period when wind is usually strong in Romania.

In order to synchronize production with consumption, a generic battery has been considered, which is charging when it is excess of produced energy compared with consumption and is discharging when there is more consumption than production. For not needing an excessively high storage resource, it has been also considered a power component named “exchange”, which is cumulating (Figure 3) the acceptable tie-line exchange with neighbourhood power systems, having an average power $P_{TIE_LINES}(\Delta T_i)$ on a specific

ΔT_i interval of one hour and a generic long-term storage represented by hourly average power $P_{LONGT_STOR}(\Delta T_i)$, the latest only consuming energy in summer period, such as a power to gas (P2G) producer (e.g. hydrogen).

The following equations have been used for simulating the storage need evolution depicted in Figure 3:

$$P_{EXCH}(\Delta T_i) = P_{TIE_LINES}(\Delta T_i) + P_{LONGT_STOR}(\Delta T_i) \quad (2)$$

$$E_{[T1,Tk]} = \int_{T1}^{Tk} (P_{PROD}(t) - P_{CONS}(t) - P_{EXCH}(t)) dt \quad (3)$$

$$E_{[T1,Tk]} \cong \sum_{i=1}^K (P_{PROD}(\Delta T_i) - P_{CONS}(\Delta T_i) - P_{EXCH}(\Delta T_i)) \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where $P_{PROD}(\Delta T_i)$ is the sum of average powers on ΔT_i intervals of one hour, for each production technology. $E_{[T1,Tk]}$ is the energy needed to be stored in batteries between T1 and Tk, where Tk is in the weekly interval [T1, T2] and takes values from 1 to 168, as 168 is the number of hours in a week.

Figure 3 – Storage resources necessary to synchronize stochastic production with consumption over the studied winter week

The maximum stored energy obtained in the selected time interval is around 70000 MWh (70 GWh) in the studied week, while the total power exchange (on tie-lines and power to gas - P2G) has been considered of maximum 1500 MW, a power level which can be supported even by the existing tie-lines capacity (no grid reinforcement is needed on tie-lines) or, when tie-lines have reduced capacity, the excess energy can be used for storing it in another form, for later use (long term storage).

This situation suggests that a consumption load for providing long-term storage based on e.g. H₂ production, combined with a moderate tie-line power exchange is needed for keeping the necessary storage resource at a lower level.

To have a more comprehensive analysis, the same upscaling has been considered for a summer week, between 1st and 7th of June 2016, with data from the same source [24].

Figure 4 shows the evolution of production and consumption considering the same upscaling of renewables and phase-out of fossil fuel based energy as has been used for the winter period.

In this way we consider also the same nominal power for PV and wind, taking into consideration that between winter and summer of year 2016 it was present the same capacity as well. By scaling up the shape of production with PV and wind, we simulate with good approximation a real scale-up of renewables, as expected in the future.

Figure 4 – Production and consumption over a whole summer week, in the June period 01-07.06.2017

The following energies have been calculated within the presented scenario:

Table 3 – Energy consumption and production during the summer week from Figure 4, based on the Table 1 upscaling factors

Description	Energy /week [GWh]	[%] from cons.
Total production	1375	113
Consumption	1215	100
Hydro	327	26.9
Nuclear	197	26.8
PV	641	52.7
Wind	203	16.7

To be observed that the high scaling of PV production, needed to accommodate the winter period, achieved a high share of 52.7% in the summer period, the share of wind production was 16.7%, specific to summer period. The figures show how well wind and PV production can complement in the Romanian environment in both winter and summer time.

Similarly to the previous case, the generic battery has been also considered, which is charging when it is excess of produced energy compared with consumption and is discharging when there is more consumption than production. The component named “Exch+P2G” has the same meaning, as it includes both tie-lines power exchange and power to gas transformations. Figure 5 shows the evolution of charging and discharging the battery (energy E in MWh) and the power used for tie-line exchange and for the long-term storage.

Figure 5 – Storage resources necessary to synchronize stochastic production with consumption over a summer week

The energy needed to be stored in this scenario was up to 75 GWh. Higher energy may be needed without tie-line exchange and without long-term storage, however the study considered the figure 4 evolution as a balanced design. It shall be pointed that the excess of energy during the summer period ask for such long-term storage technologies, as in summer there is more PV energy than in winter time. This situation gives a similarity with the agriculture, where crops are particularly obtainable also in summer period, when the sun has higher average intensity.

Additional analysis has been made with other weeks spread over the year. Figure 6 shows the evolution of energy needed to be stored over 7 days for eight different weekly intervals, including the ones already analysed in more detail.

Figure 6 – Storage resources necessary over different weeks over the whole year 2017

One can see that in all cases the needed energy to be stored on weekly basis is less than 90 GWh. This result shows that a total storage resource can mitigate the production and consumption in Romania on weekly medium term, while power exchange with neighborhood countries and long-term storage based on technologies such as power to gas, which may ask for total powers between 1.5 and 3.5 GW. The evolution of stored energy has conventional minus sign, which correspond to absorption of energy, opposed to production energy production which considered positive.

III. REVIEW OF STORAGE FOR THE POWER SYSTEM NEEDS

Simplified calculations made in the section III suggest that it is possible to obtain 100% CO₂ free production over the entire year by requesting corresponding upscale of PV and wind production and around 70 to 85 GWh of storage resources, to cope with the production-consumption behaviour. A higher value of 100 GWh will cover better even more special situations. This means an equivalent of 10 to 12 hours of national energy consumption relying only on the energy produced by the generic battery, for a slightly increased consumption of 1 GW average power, comparing with today value of consumption, increase which can be expected e.g. due to high electrical vehicles (EV) penetration.

Such storage resources will be needed to store extra energy for days with poor renewables, using a combination of short term and medium term storage technology, such as Li-Ion and redox flow batteries. The needed energy for accidentally very low renewables situation may be solved with basic production in nuclear, future carbon-capture-plants (if they will demonstrate economic solutions) and hydro, for a basic band of at least 40% of total production, helped by the pan-European

exchange which can be in the range of 1000 to 2000 MW. The pan-European network will act in two ways: making the sum of power with renewables more constant over Europe and acting as an additional virtual storage mean.

To summarize, we can consider that the necessary medium-term storage to cope with 100% CO₂ in Romania will need around 100 GWh of battery storage capacity in most of the cases, when analysing medium time frames of one week.

IV. STORAGE NEEDED FOR THE EVS

According to [25], the Romanian park of passenger's cars in use in Romania was in 2014 of 4.906 million cars, meaning 4.5% from approx./ 251 million in whole EU and 246 cars/1000 inhabitants. Moreover, total trucks in use were 843.8 thousand, as being 5.8% from the total 443 thousand in 2014 all over EU.

In in recent short period (2016 to ongoing 2018), EVs hit a new wave, as being announced in a short period many EV models and plans for future from different manufacturers.

Battery cost dropped twice in last two-three years and this allowed that current EVs are sold with a capacity between 30 and 100 kWh. An average of 40 kWh may be considered today and this may evolve easily till 2020 at 80 kWh, while price is expected to drop again twice. 75 kWh are already listed to allow autonomy of 500 km, while 100 kWh will support at least 650 km, both being already compatible with some of today gas-bases ICEs. 2030 may see higher storage capacity per each EV, between 150 and 200 kWh, which will beat today ICE expectations (more than 1000 km per one charge).

Very optimists argue that 50% of sales will be in pure EV domain by 2025, while more pessimists see that this will happen 5 to 15 years later. A 100% sales of electric vehicles is foreseen sometime between 2035 and 2050, depending on the source, which may replace the whole park of today vehicles around year 2050. The number of today 1 billion EVs will evolve eventually towards 2 billion, due to evolution in markets such as China and India, or will decrease at less than 500 million, due to massive self-driving deployment, which will make car-sharing the default way of using cars.

If we assume by averaging different perspectives that we will have 100% EVs by 2045-2050, with 100 kWh battery capacity per EV (it can be even 50% higher at that time), and that the number of total cars will remain the same as today (a combination of car-sharing able to reduce the number, with the trend to have more care users users), we will have the following total storage capacity embedded only in cars:

$$E_{EV_TOT} = \sum E_{EV} = 5 \times 10^6 \text{ cars} \times 100 \text{ kWh/car} = 500 \text{ GWh}$$

It can be seen that for the Romanian case, the EV capacity in storage (500 GWh, estimated in this section) is 5 times higher than the needed capacity in power system domain (100 GWh, estimated above).

This simplified calculation shows that the storage need for deploying 100% EVs is much more significant than the storage needed for attending 100% CO₂ free electrical energy.

Figure 7 shows an optimistic and a pessimistic scenario regarding EV penetration: up to 100% in 2050 and up to only 80% at the same date. Moreover, an evolution of V2G participation is proposed, from 2% in 2025 up to 30% in 2050, based on evolving technology and applications to take advantage of the EV battery storage for power systems needs.

Figure 7 – EV evolution scenarios (optimistic and pessimistic) and possible use for power systems by using V2G technologies

In the two proposed scenarios the needed storage resource of 100 GWh for a 100% CO₂ free electrical energy is reached in 2040 and 2045 respectively through V2G support.

It can be deduced that the transformation in electrical domain will be driven by electrical vehicles, and not by itself. With 50% of deployed EVs having vehicle to grid (V2G) features, their batteries, either used for charging (acting as loads and having the potential of huge demand response services), or used to help the grid with back-injection of power, we may have already solved the storage need in power systems, mitigating a 100% CO₂ free production, with high stochastic share of renewables such as PV or wind farms while posing some conditions for the EVs scheduling. With 100% EV deployment, there are already significant storage resources to mitigate all time the power system needs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The paper aims to investigate the necessary capacity in storage resources for both power systems and EVs transportation domain.

With the simplified calculations in selected periods of the year using the Romanian profile of production and consumption, it has been suggested that are necessary around 100 GWh of short term and medium-term (e.g. up to one week) storage resources. Additional long-term storage in hydrogen or other energy carrier may be also necessary. Similarly, the battery capacity for changing entire park of today ICE vehicles in EVs is estimated to a need of around 500 GWh of batteries. It is a 5x difference for the storage need in EVs. This situation gives a synthetic image of the ratio between the two challenging targets, in terms of storage needs. The findings

suggest that it will be much easier to reach 100% CO₂ free production in terms of storage needs, by promoting an ambitious policy towards 100% EVs on the roads. In fact, it can be inferred that reaching even a 50% EV penetration is similar to have a 100% renewables deployment, in terms of needed storage to mitigate stochastic RES production.

Moreover, projected plans of having in Romania hydro pumped storage resources such as at Tarnița, with a potential of around 12-15 GWh, is highly overpassed by the need in power systems for around 100 GWh in storage for mitigating medium term (e.g. a week timeframe) RES production and by the storage potential of EVs of up to 500 GWh, if it is used in a combination of demand response (charging when the system needs more loads) and vehicle to grid (V2G), to inject power when it is a shortage of production in the power system.

As PVs will continue to reduce the specific cost of installed kW, it is highly expected that the PV high expansion, together with additional but more moderate expansion in wind generation, will be possible to be deployed and their stochastic behaviour mitigated by teaming the high EV and wind penetration with a high EVs adoption, to help reaching the 100% CO₂ free production target, through an intelligent use of EV's storage means. With this awareness it becomes clearer that EVs need charging with clean energy, to justify the shift to clean transportation, and that the clean energy can be implemented with huge battery resources which can be highly available from EVs. It is a synergy between the two segments of the economy which shows the high impact of EVs, as main drivers for a clean transportation and clean energy generation in the same time, a situation which has been assessed on the Romanian case with positive results.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research work leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 731155 Storage4Grid project and of the grant of the Romanian National Authority for Scientific Research and Innovation, CNCS/CCCDI – UEFISCDI, project no. PN-III-P3-3.6-H2020-2016-0080-ID 731155, Storage4Grid within PNCDI III.

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